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Review Article

NATURAL COMPOUNDS THAT INHIBIT PROTEIN GLYCATION: A REVIEW FOR RECENT FINDINGS

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Abstract:

Diabetes Mellitus is a chronic, lifelong disease currently impacting people throughout the world. A fundamental cause of Diabetes Mellitus: Non-enzymatic protein glycosylation (glycation) contributes to a group of metabolic diseases, including diabetes-associated late complications, atherosclerosis, chronic renal failure, Alzheimer's disease and inflammatory arthritis. It has been hypothesized that inhibition of glycation may prevent the diseases associated with diabetes. Inhibitors of glycation have been explored for several decades, chiefly using in vitro models, which resulted in discovery of different natural compounds capable of forestalling glycation, such as antioxidants, polysaccharide, metal chelators and peptides. Many peptides released from different proteins have proven to possess physiological functions besides their nutrient roles. Even the results of in vitro studies are not directly applicable on the in vivo situation due to differences in the conditions, mechanism of glycation and bioavailability issues. In this review article, we briefly discuss the mechanism of advanced glycation end products (AGEs) in promoting pathogenesis and then present the recent findings concerning the role of plant-based inhibitors and amino acid peptides in decreasing the formations of AGEs. These findings suggest that enrichment of diet with natural, anti-glycating agents may reduce glycation and as a consequence, diabetic complications.

Keywords: Glycation, Diabetes, Hyperglycemia, AGEs-inhibitors, Retinopathy.

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INTRODUCTION:

For the past few years, there is a steep rise in the incidences of diabetes around the world. Globally, an estimated 422 million adults had diabetes in 2014, compared to 108 million in 1980. The global prevalence (age-standardized) of diabetes has climbed up from 4.7% to 8.5% since 1980 among the adults [1]. Saudi Arabia is one of the 19 countries and territories of the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, which has the seventh highest rate of prevalence of diabetes. There were approximately 3.4 million cases of diabetes in Saudi Arabia in 2015, and according to a recent estimate, almost 24.4% of the adult population is suffering from diabetes mellitus [2]. The term “diabetes mellitus” describes a group of metabolic disorders with varied etiology characterized by chronic hyperglycemia with disturbances of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism resulting from the defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. The effects of diabetes mellitus include long-term damage, dysfunction, and failure of various organs, especially the eyes, kidneys, nerves, heart, and blood vessels [3] [4]. Long-term complications of diabetes include: retinopathy with potential loss of vision [5]; nephropathy leading to renal failure [6]; peripheral neuropathy with risk of foot ulcers, amputations, and Charcot joints [7]; autonomic neuropathy causing gastrointestinal [8], genitourinary [9] and cardiovascular symptoms [10] and sexual dysfunction [11, 12]. Diabetic patients have an increased incidence of atherosclerotic cardiovascular [13], peripheral arterial [14], and cerebrovascular disease [15]. The long-term effects of diabetes are mostly due to protein glycation, also called the Maillard reaction that impairs the function of biomolecules [16]. The Maillard reaction was identified by a French scientist Louis Camille Maillard, in 1912. He discovered yellow-brown colors while sugar was heated with amino acids [17]. This reaction was introduced in the food industry for improving aroma, texture, and color of the food stuff and scientists discovered that this reaction also takes place in *in vivo* and is currently involved in the pathogenesis of various diseases [18–20].

GLYCATION AND ADVANCED GLYCATION END PRODUCTS (AGES)

Maillard reaction, also referred to as Glycation is a complex cascade of reactions. The reaction is typically slow at physiological conditions since it does not involve an enzyme catalyst, it requires several days or weeks to get completed [16]. The reaction starts when the aldehyde on reducing sugars,

such as glucose, fructose, and ribose, is attacked by the terminal amino groups of proteins, nucleic acids [21] and phospholipids [22], forming an unstable Schiff base [23]. The Schiff base then undergoes a slow structural rearrangement (Amadori rearrangement/ Heyns rearrangement), and the reaction proceeds to a relatively more stable, irreversible Amadori products or keto-amines, for instance, HbA1c [24].

Oxidative decomposition of the Amadori products leads to the accumulation of a wide range of highly reactive intermediates like carbonyl and dicarbonyl compounds also known as oxoaldehydes. The products of these carbonyl compounds include 3-deoxyglucosone (3-dG), glyoxal (GO) and methylglyoxal (MGO) glycolaldehyde, 1-deoxyglucosone, 4, 5- dioxo pentose, and 5, 6-dioxohexose [25]. The MGO formation also occurs by a non-oxidative process in anaerobic glycolysis [26] and by oxidative degradation of polyunsaturated fatty acids [22]. The highly electrophilic nature of these dicarbonyl compounds makes them react relatively faster with guanidine, arginine and lysine residues, amino and sulfhydryl functional moieties of proteins to produce different irreversible adducts [23]. Furthermore, modifications of these glycation products, such as rearrangement, oxidation, polymerization and cleavage, produces irreversible conjugates known as AGEs [27]. AGEs include N^ε-(carboxymethyl) lysine (CML), N^ε-(carboxylethyl)lysine (CEL), S-(carboxymethyl) cysteine (CMC), pyrroline, 3-deoxyglucosone-derived imidazolium crosslink, pentosidine, glucosepane, glyoxal lysine dimer, crosslinks and fluorolink [19]. As a result, Intra- and inter-molecular heterocyclic cross-linking and fragmentation of proteins occur. AGEs, senescent macroprotein heterogeneous moieties are the final products of the glycation process. The final products of the glycation process, the AGEs, have greater thermostability. Since AGEs are the final product of non-enzymatic glycosylation process, therefore it can be produced both in *in vivo* and *in vitro*. Formation of AGEs in a living organism is concentration-dependent and hence enhanced in hyperglycemic conditions while dietary intake of exogenous AGEs also contributes to the accumulation of AGEs and pathogenesis of AGEs related diseases. AGEs are found in some foods which are formed in normal conditions and can form in food during cooking, especially more in modern diets because they are largely heat-processed through frying, baking, roasting and comparatively less in foods prepared by boiling, steaming and stewing [28]. Smoking is another strong source of AGEs; It was reported that glycotoxins, which promote AGEs formation were isolated from aqueous extracts of

tobacco and cigarette smoke [29]. Some proteins in the blood serum of smokers were modified by nicotine which is a metabolite of tobacco nicotine [24]. Skin of smokers had higher AGEs compared to non-smokers [30]. An overview of the various routes of AGEs formation and its toxic effects in different organs is depicted in **Fig. 1**.

MECHANISM OF AGES RELATED PATHOGENESIS

AGEs are implicated in diabetes mellitus, and its complications as reported by Rahbar *et al*. The elevated HbA1c, one of the Amadori product of hemoglobin in diabetic patients is a potent source of development of diabetes mellitus [31]. In diabetes, glucose modified-HSA resulted in AGEs formation and resulted in deleterious impairment in biochemical, electrochemical, spectroscopic, optical and fluidity properties of HSA at high concentrations of glucose [32]. It was proved that glycation of insulin and proinsulin occurs in the pancreas during the point of insulin synthesis and storage leading to insulin resistance and reduced glucose uptake [33]. Low-density lipoprotein is also glycated in diabetic atherosclerosis and is not recognized by the LDL receptor contributing to the hyperlipidemias, accelerated foam cell formation and glycation of high-density lipoproteins, hence, reducing its function during cholesterol transport [34]. Glycation of myelin has been identified in Diabetic neuropathy, and this modification of myelin stimulates macrophages to secrete proteases leading to nerve demyelination [12]. Immunohistochemical analysis revealed that AGEs were detected in diabetic renal tissue, wherein, thickening of the basement membrane, expansion of the mesangium developed resulting in renal failure. AGEs stimulate the release of transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β), which increases the synthesis of collagen matrix components and may account for the thickening of the basement membrane in diabetic nephropathy [35]. AGEs were also noticed in retinal blood vessel walls and were hypothesized to be involved in up-regulating RAGE mRNA levels. This cause pericytes to undergo apoptosis through triggering oxidative stress and finally severe visual impairment leading to diabetic retinopathy [36]. Lens crystalline was studied in diabetic cataract, and it was found that

glycation of lens crystallin causes conformational changes, aggregation, crosslinking and opacification at the end stage [37]. A Recent study has shown that AGEs accumulation leads RAGE to stimulate both IL-33 release and ILC2 accumulation in the lungs to promote chronic and acute allergic airway disease [8]. AGEs in the human ovary may account for some age-related features of ovarian dysfunction, including impaired vascularization and consequent hypoxia due to reduced intake of nutrients by follicle cells [38]. Eventually, AGEs affect nearly all types of cell (**Fig. 1**) and molecules in the body and play a vital role as proinflammatory mediators.

Fig. 1: Formation of AGEs and its toxic effects in different organ systems.

INHIBITORS OF AGES FORMATION

Phytochemical AGEs inhibitors

Phytochemicals are produced by plants through primary or secondary metabolism. They generally have biological activity in the plant host and play a major role in plants to help them thrive or defense against competitors, predators or pathogens [39, 40]. Phytochemicals have been used for centuries as traditional medicines and studied widely for their numerous biological activities such as anticancer, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and antiglycation. In order to provide an efficient therapeutic strategy for diabetes and its associated complications, natural antiglycation compounds which have limited side effects have been isolated from plants and widely studied. We have discussed listed the recent findings on phytochemical AGEs inhibitors in **Table. 1**.

Table 1: Overview of the recent findings on phytochemical AGEs inhibitors.

PLANT-BASED PHYTOCHEMICAL AGES INHIBITORS						
Source	Solvent	Active component	Objective	Methodology for analysis	Results	Reference(s)
Grape skin	---	phenolic content	Muffins	Determination of carboxymethyl lysine.	Reduced CML	[41]
Punica granatum Linn.	Methanol	steroids, triterpenoids, Glycosides, flavonoids, saponins and tannins. Phenolic content	Rat	Serum AGEs	Reduced AGE	[42]
Cissus quadrangularis Linn	Methanol	ethyl acetate fraction	Rat	HbA1c assay	Inhibited Glycation	[43]
Coptidis rhizoma	---	Berberine	Rat	Immunohistochemistry for RAGE.	Reduced RAGE	[35]
Green tea	---	epigallocatechin 3-gallate	Mice	Serum AGEs and tissue AGEs Western blot for RAGE.	Inhibited Glycation Reduced RAGE	[44]
garlic	Water	Organosulphur constituents	Rat	Immunohistochemistry for RAGE.	Reduced RAGE	[45]
Terminalia chebula Retz.	Ethyl acetate	chebulic acid	LX-2 cells	LX-2 cells were treated with glyceraldehyde-derived advanced glycation end-products and chebulic acid.	Inhibited Glycation	[46]
Artocarpus communis	---	flavonoid content	(HCT116 cells THP-1 monocytes)	BSA glycation test with glyceraldehyde. Western blot for RAGE	Inhibited glycation reduced RAGE	[47]
chilli peppers origin	---	Capsaicin	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose.	Inhibited Glycation	[48]
Osteomeles schwerinae C. K. Schneid.	Ethanol	phenolic content	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose and fructose. AGE-RAGE binding using ELISA. Detection of live cell-based AGE-BSA/RAGE binding.	Inhibited Glycation	[49]
Gynura procumbens leaves	Ethanol	phenolic content flavonoid content	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose.	Inhibited Glycation	[50]
heartwood of Pterocarpus marsupium	Ethanol	phenolic content flavonoid content	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with fructose.	Inhibited Glycation	[51]

garlic ginger thyme parsley curry leaves peppermint turmeric onion green onion scallion coriander	Ethanol Water	Tannins Saponins Phlobatannins Anthraquinones Terpenoids Diterpenes Steroids Flavonoid phenolics	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose. BSA glycation test with fructose.	Inhibited Glycation	[52]
Canarium album L.	Water, ethanol, methanol, acetone, Ethyl acetate	Triterpenoid content phenolic content flavonoid content	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose. Determination of protein thiol group.	Inhibited Glycation	[53]
Camellia nitidissima Chi	Ethanol	dichloromethane fraction ethyl acetate fraction n-butanol fraction water fraction	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose and MGO Methylglyoxal scavenging assay.	Inhibited Glycation	[54]
Annona crassiflora Mart.	Ethanol	hexane, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, n-butanol and water fractions	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with fructose.	Inhibited Glycation	[55]
Carpobrotus edulis Foeniculum vulgare	Water Ethanol	phenolic content flavonoid content	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose. Determination of fructosamine by NBT assay, Determination of protein carbonyl content.	Inhibited Glycation	[56] [57]
Aphloia theiformis (Vahl.) Benn	Methanol Water	hexane, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, and n-butanol fractions	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with fructose	Inhibited Glycation	[58]

Coccinia grandis	Methanol	phenolic content flavonoid content saponins and dietary fiber content	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with fructose Determination of fructosamine Protein bound carbonyl groups determined using DNPH. TNBSA assay to determine lysine modification Quantification. Circular dichroism measurements for the changes in the secondary structure of BSA	Inhibited Glycation	[59]
Ocimum americanum	Methanol, Water	phenolic content	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose	Inhibited Glycation	[60]
Red ginseng	Water	phenolic content		apolipoprotein A-I glycation test with fructose.	Inhibited Glycation	[61]
Algae	Water	phenolic content	<i>In vitro</i>	Lysine-Glucose Maillard reaction assay. BSA glycation test with glucose MGO.	Inhibited Glycation	[62]
sugarcane molasses	Water	phenolic content	<i>In vitro</i>	Lysine-Glucose Maillard reaction assay	Reduced CML and CEL	[63]
cruciferous vegetables		Sinigrin(glucosinolale)	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose, MGO. Determination of fructosamine Protein-bound carbonyl groups determined using DNPH. TNBSA assay to determine lysine modification Quantification. Circular dichroism measurements for the changes in the secondary structure of BSA	Inhibited Glycation	[64]
Jujube fruit Ripe fruit	Water	phenolic content flavonoid content	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with fructose	Inhibited Glycation	[65]
phyllanthus emblica Cassia Auriculata	Water	phenolic content	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose	Inhibited Glycation	[66]
Ilex paraguariensis	Water	chlorogenic acid	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with fructose and glucose	Inhibited Glycation	[67]

Syzygium jambolanum and Cephalaria indica	Water	Glycosides phenolic content flavonoid content	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with fructose Determination of fructosamine by NBT assay, Determination of protein carbonyl content, Determination of protein thiol group Determination of free amino groups	Inhibited Glycation	[68] [66]
vanilla bean		Vanillin Resveratrol	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose, MGO Determination of protein carbonyl content, Determination of fructosamine by NBT assay Circular dichroism measurements for the changes in the secondary structure of BSA SDS page electrophoresis for glycation	Inhibited Glycation	[69] [70]
Houttuynia cordata		Quercetin	<i>In vitro</i>	HSA <i>in vitro</i> glycation test with glucose and glyoxal Circular dichroism measurements for the changes in the secondary structure of HSA Hemoglobin- δ -gluconolactone assay Methylglyoxal-HSA reactivity assay	Inhibited Glycation	[71] [72] [73] [74]

Phytochemicals extracted from medicinally used plants have shown promising antiglycation activity in *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Methanolic extract from *Coccinia grandis* was tested in an antiglycation assay in a BSA-fructose model. A concentration of 0.5 mg/ml showed significant AGEs inhibition after 28 days. Levels of fructosamine and protein carbonyl content in the BSA-fructose system decreased to the same degree as in aminoguanidine group [59]. In another study, ApoA-I glycation with fructose was inhibited by 100 μ g/ml of Red ginseng water extract within 48 hours [61]. However, in a study performed by Kuda and colleagues, Algae aqueous extract interfered Lysine-Glucose Maillard reaction and inhibited BSA glycation with glucose and MGO [62]. In a separate study reported, Quercetin was extracted from *Houttuynia cordata* and evaluated for antiglycation activity in HSA- Glucose, glyoxal glycation model and it was demonstrated that AGEs formation was lowered and the changes in the

secondary structure of HSA decreased [71, 72]. In a recent study, Flavonoid content prepared from *Artocarpus communis* was used to treat HCT116 colon cancer cells, it was observed that the malignancy enhanced by AGEs was decreased after the treatment along with the decline in the levels of and RAGE [47]. Additionally, Ethyl acetate fraction- chebulic acid- from *Terminalia chebula retz* inhibited AGEs induced hepatic fibrosis in LX-2 cells modulating Nrf2 translocation via ERK pathway [46]. Also, AGEs inhibitory activity of Epigallocatechin 3-gallate purified from green tea was studied in *in vivo*, the plasma AGEs level in HFD induced obesity mice were decreased accompanied by the inhibition of RAGE expression in liver [44].

Plant-based polysaccharides AGEs inhibitors:

Polysaccharides are natural polymeric carbohydrate molecules formed by glycosidic linkages between monosaccharide units. If all the monosaccharides in a

polysaccharide are of the same type, then the polysaccharide is called a homopolysaccharide, but if more than one type of monosaccharide is present, it is referred to as a heteropolysaccharide. Polysaccharides are stable, safe, non-toxic, non-carcinogenic components of plants and microorganisms with diverse bioactivities, such as anticancer, anticoagulant, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-thrombotic, hypoglycemic and antioxidant activities [75]. Recent findings on plant-based polysaccharide inhibitors have been listed in **Table 2**. Recently, many types of research have been conducted globally on polysaccharides, due to its high antioxidant and antiglycation activity. In a unique study, XU *et al.*, extracted polysaccharides from black currant, consisting of galacturonic acid, xylose, mannose, glucose, and galactose. A concentration of 0.2 mg/ml showed significant antiglycation activity, and interestingly, the inhibitory action on protein glycation was more efficient in the later phases of AGEs and dicarbonyl compounds formation [76]. In a different study, polysaccharides

extracted from *Boletus snicus* comprised of a large amount of glucose, uronic acid and a small amount of mannose, galactose, arabinose, glucosamine hydrochloride and glucuronic acid, exhibited significant antiglycation activity at lower concentrations [77]. In an another study, the mechanism of polysaccharides on antiglycation was attributed to its structure, M.Chouch *et al.*, extracted polysaccharides from *Opuntia ficus indica* and degraded them by sonication from 6,800,000 to 14,000 g/mol; they discovered that the polysaccharides degraded for 2 and 3 h showed even better antioxidant and antiglycation activities [78]. However, the antiglycation activity of polysaccharides is still unclear. This might be due to its structure, such as the type of glycosyl linkage, type of monosaccharides or other composition and also the molecular weight. Hence, the further in-depth study is needed to unravel the complex antiglycation mechanisms involved. In short, polysaccharides may be a promising drug candidate in the near future for inhibiting glycation.

Table 2: Polysaccharide inhibitors as antiglycation agents: Recent findings.

PLANT-BASED POLYSACCHARIDES AGES INHIBITORS						
Source	Solvent	Active component	Objective	Methodology for analysis	Results	Reference(s)
Benincasa hispida (Thunb.) Cogn.	Water	Polysaccharides	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose.	Inhibited Glycation	[79]
Opuntia ficus indica	Water	Polysaccharides	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with galactose.	Inhibited Glycation	[78]
black currant	Enzyme solution	Polysaccharides	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose. TNBSA assay to determine lysine modification. Quantification. Determination of protein carbonyl content.	Inhibited Glycation	[76]
Boletus snicus	Water	Polysaccharides	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose. TNBSA assay to determine lysine modification. Quantification. Determination of protein carbonyl content.	Inhibited Glycation	[77]

Raspberry (<i>R. idaeus</i> L.) fruits	Water	Polysaccharides	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose. TNBSA assay to determine lysine modification Quantification. Determination of protein carbonyl content.	Inhibited Glycation	[80]
Pueraria lobata roots	Water	Polysaccharides	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose.	Inhibited Glycation	[81]
Dendrobium huoshanense	Water	Polysaccharides	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with glucose. TNBSA assay to determine lysine modification Quantification. Determination of protein carbonyl content.	Inhibited Glycation	[82]
Polygonum multiflorum Thunb	Ethanol Water	Polysaccharides	<i>In vitro</i>	BSA glycation test with MGO.	Inhibited Glycation	[83]

Amino Acid and Peptide inhibitors:

Different peptides and amino acids also have the potential to reduce the formation of AGEs, if they are more reactive with reducing sugars than proteins and phospholipids. While studying the reactions of various peptides and amino acids with aldehydes, Zhou and Decker found that 5mM histidine reduced headspace trans-2-hexanal by only 8% when mixed with 0.5 mM of trans-2-hexanal and 5mM of β -alanine could not reduce headspace trans-2-hexanal at all. Glutathione was able to quench trans-2-hexanal and trans,trans-2,4-hexadienal by 47 and 21% respectively at glutathione concentrations of only 1 mM [84]. While in a different study, Hobart et al. found that histidine alone was more effective than carnosine in preventing glycation induced crosslinking of cytosolic aspartate aminotransferase, ceasing the formation at a 1:1 antiglycation agent to causative agent ratio; while Carnosine needed a 50:1 ratio to prevent protein modification by methylglyoxal [85]. In a study of yam hydrolysates, Han et al. compared the dipeptides asparagine-tryptophan and glutamine-tryptophan to carnosine, homocarnosine, and glutathione in their ability to prevent glycation of bovine serum albumin with galactose. Carnosine inhibited glycation

approximately the same as asparagine-tryptophan, homocarnosine, and glutathione, interestingly, all of these were more effective than glutamine-tryptophan. At a concentration of 50 μ M, carnosine was more effective than asparagine-tryptophan followed by homocarnosine, but glutathione and glutamine-tryptophan showed no such effect. When glucose was the reducing sugar, and 100 μ M of the peptide was used, glutathione exhibited more activity than homocarnosine, which in turn was more effective than both asparagine-tryptophan and glutamine-tryptophan, which were almost equivalent. However, the antiglycation activity of carnosine was less than glutathione, homocarnosine, asparagine-tryptophan, and glutamine-tryptophan. At a concentration of 50 μ M, asparagine-tryptophan and glutamine-tryptophan had negligible effects, while glutathione showed better results than carnosine. Pre-treatment of cells with asparagine-tryptophan and glutamine-tryptophan resulted in an increase of cell survival from 50% to 90% when stress was applied with methylglyoxal (one of the common reactive carbonyl species in the body). The various actions of the synthesized peptides from different studies and their active components are presented in **Table. 3**.

Table 3: Recent update on amino acid and peptide inhibitors as antiglycation agents.

AMINO ACID AND PEPTIDE INHIBITORS					
Source	Active component	Methodology	Analysis	Results	Reference(s)
Synthesized amino acid	Histidine	Addition of histidine to glyceraldehyde in 20:1 ratio and cytosolic aspartate aminotransferase before incubation.	Protein electrophoresis	20 mM caused 60% inhibition of crosslinking	[85]
Synthesized amino acid	B alanine	Addition of B alanine to glyceraldehyde in 10:1 ratio and cytosolic aspartate aminotransferase before incubation.	Protein electrophoresis	5 mM caused 36% inhibition of crosslinking	[85]
Synthesized Peptide	Anserine	20 mM of compound was added to previously glycated Glucose-ethylamine.	Nuclear magnetic resonance	20mM of anserine was able to reverse early glycation	[86]
Synthesized Peptide	asparagine-tryptophan	50 or 100 μ M of peptide was added to bovine serum albumin and galactose or bovine serum albumin and glucose and heated.	sodium dodecyl sulphate–polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and an anticarbocymethyllysine antibody	100 μ m reduced carbocymethyllysine to 30.7% of the control in galactose system and to 63.2% in glucose system	[87]
Synthesized Peptide	glutamine-tryptophan	50 or 100 μ M of peptide was added to bovine serum albumin and galactose or bovine serum albumin and glucose and heated.	sodium dodecyl sulphate–polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and an anticarbocymethyllysine antibody	100 μ m reduced carbocymethyllysine to 14.8% of the control in galactose system and to 58.8% in glucose system	[87]
Synthesized Peptide	Carnosine	20 mM of compound was added to previously glycated Glucose-ethylamine	Nuclear magnetic resonance	20mM of Carnosine was able to reverse early glycation	[86]
Synthesized Peptide	Carnosine	A crystallin was incubated with 10 mM ribose or deoxyribose with or without the addition of Carnosine	sodium dodecyl sulphate–polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis	50mM Carnosine prevented glycation entirely	[88]
Synthesized Peptide	Carnosine	Addition of Carnosine to glyceraldehyde in 10:1 ratio and cytosolic aspartate aminotransferase before incubation.	Protein electrophoresis	5 mM caused 68% inhibition of crosslinking	[85]
Synthesized Peptide	Carnosine	50 or 100 μ M of peptide was added to bovine serum albumin and galactose or bovine serum albumin and glucose and heated and carbocymethyllysine was detected with an antibody.	sodium dodecyl sulphate–polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis	100 μ m reduced carbocymethyllysine to 13% of the control in galactose system and to 68.5% in glucose system	[87]

Synthesized Peptide	Carnosine	Streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats given oral dose of 1g Carnosine /kg body weight/day	quantitative retinal morphometry, analysis of retinal proteins, Histological examination of retinal paraffin sections	Oral dose of Carnosine Prevented retinal vascular damage primarily by altered gene expression	[89]
Synthesized Peptide	Carnosine	A diet composed of 0.001%, 0.01%, or 0.1% of Carnosine by mass was given to 2-deoxy-D-glucose induced diabetic rats	Blood sampling	0.01% or 0.001% Carnosine suppressed hyperglycemia,	[90]
Synthesized Peptide	Homocarnosine	50 or 100 μ M of peptide was added to bovine serum albumin and galactose or bovine serum albumin and glucose and heated	sodium dodecyl sulphate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and an anticarbocymethyllysine antibody	100 μ m reduced carbocymethyllysine to 17.8% of the control in galactose system and to 49% in glucose system	[87]
Synthesized Peptide	Glutathione	50 or 100 μ M of peptide was added to bovine serum albumin and galactose or bovine serum albumin and glucose and heated	sodium dodecyl sulphate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis and an anticarbocymethyllysine antibody	100 μ m reduced carbocymethyllysine to 17.8% of the control in galactose system and to 49% in glucose system	[87]
Synthesized Peptide	Glucagon-like peptide-1	Murine podocytes	Western blotting	RAGE was down regulated	[91]
Garlic	c-glutamylcysteine derivatives	Maillard reaction systems with glucose L-lysine mixture	CML determination	Decreased CML	[92]

Alhamdani et al. studied the protection of human peritoneal mesothelial cells from the toxic effects of peritoneal dialysis fluid, which contained both glucose and glucose degradation products; both of which can produce AGEs, using many potential amino acids and dipeptides. It was reported that as far as protective effects are concerned, carnosine was more effective than homocarnosine followed by β -alanine, anserine and histidine [93]. Histidine and anserine both showed toxicity to the cells, with histidine displaying cell toxicity without a protective effect in the presence of the peritoneal dialysis fluid. Hipkiss et al. incubated 50 mM of various peptides with 500 mM of different sugars [88]. After HPLC analysis at specific times, the researchers found that homocarnosine showed lower reactivity with reducing sugars when compared to carnosine and thus may be less effective in decreasing early glycation.

The Inhibition of AGEs by amino acids and small peptides vary in each study. Differences between the models chosen, such as the type and amount of sugar used, the amount of protective agent added, the protein target and consideration of toxicity play a

crucial role in concluding the results. There is an emerging trend that homocarnosine is less reactive than carnosine, which is less responsive than histidine with glucose and reactive carbonyls such as methylglyoxal. Carnosine and Homocarnosine have an additional advantage in that they display less toxicity than glycated amino acids in cell models. There are numerous sources of proteins and peptides that could have potential to decrease AGE formation. However, varied results between current studies indicate that more research is needed to identify which peptide structures that have the ability to reduce AGEs formation.

CONCLUSION:

These findings suggest that there is an urgent need to address the issue of bioavailability and fill up the void between the results obtained in *in vitro* and *in vivo* platforms for better clarification in further studies. In addition, many studies have found that the use of more than one plant-based antiglycation agent synergistically can give better results than a single agent. Further, the pace of research should be way ahead than the increasing incidences of glycation-

related diseases to develop functional foods from the natural sources.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no financial conflict of interest.

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REFERENCES:

1. World Health Organization. (2016). Global Report on Diabetes. Isbn, 978, 88. doi:ISBN 978 92 4 156525 7
2. Bani, I. A. (2015). Prevalence, Knowledge, Attitude and Practices of Diabetes Mellitus among Jazan Population, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA). *Journal of Diabetes Mellitus*, 5(2), 115–122. doi:10.4236/jdm.2015.52014
3. American Diabetes Association. (2012). Diagnosis and Classification of Diabetes Mellitus. *Diabetes Care*, 35(Supplement_1), S64–S71. doi:10.2337/dc12-s064
4. Alberti, K. G. M. M., & Zimmet, P. Z. (1998). Definition, diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus and its complications. Part 1: diagnosis and classification of diabetes mellitus. Provisional report of a WHO Consultation. *Diabetic Medicine*, 15(7), 539–553. doi:10.1002/(SICI)1096-9136(199807)15:7<539::AID-DIA668>3.0.CO;2-S
5. Chen, M., Curtis, T. M., & Stitt, a W. (2013). Advanced Glycation End Products and Diabetic Retinopathy. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 20(26), 3234–3240. doi:10.2174/09298673113209990025
6. Uribarri, J. (2003). Restriction of Dietary Glycotoxins Reduces Excessive Advanced Glycation End Products in Renal Failure Patients. *Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*, 14(3), 728–731. doi:10.1097/01.ASN.0000051593.41395.B9
7. Jack, M., & Wright, D. (2012). Role of advanced glycation endproducts and glyoxalase I in diabetic peripheral sensory neuropathy. *Translational Research*, 159(5), 355–365. doi:10.1016/j.trsl.2011.12.004
8. Oczypok, E. A., Milutinovic, P. S., Alcorn, J. F., Khare, A., Crum, L. T., Manni, M. L., ... Oury, T. D. (2015). Pulmonary receptor for advanced glycation end-products promotes asthma pathogenesis through IL-33 and accumulation of group 2 innate lymphoid cells. *Journal of Allergy and Clinical Immunology*, 136(3), 747–756.e4. doi:10.1016/j.jaci.2015.03.011
9. Yang, S., Pinney, S. M., Mallick, P., Ho, S.-M.,

Bracken, B., & Wu, T. (2015). Impact of Oxidative Stress Biomarkers and Carboxymethyllysine (an Advanced Glycation End Product) on Prostate Cancer: A Prospective Study. *Clinical Genitourinary Cancer*, 13(5), e347–e351. doi:10.1016/j.clgc.2015.04.004

10. Tam, L., Shang, Q., Li, E. K., Wong, S., Li, R.-J., Lee, K., ... Yu, C.-M. (2013). Serum Soluble Receptor for Advanced Glycation End Products Levels and Aortic Augmentation Index in Early Rheumatoid Arthritis—A Prospective Study. *Seminars in Arthritis and Rheumatism*, 42(4), 333–345. doi:10.1016/j.semarthrit.2012.07.002

11. Edwards, J. L., Edwards, J. L., Vincent, A. M., Vincent, A. M., Cheng, H. T., Cheng, H. T., ... Feldman, E. L. (2008). Diabetic neuropathy: Mechanisms to management. *Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 120(1), 1–34. doi:10.1016/j.pharmthera.2008.05.005

12. Thornalley, P. J. (2002). Glycation in diabetic neuropathy: characteristics, consequences, causes, and therapeutic options. *International review of neurobiology*, 50, 37–57. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12198817>

13. Stirban, A., Gawlowski, T., & Roden, M. (2014). Vascular effects of advanced glycation endproducts: Clinical effects and molecular mechanisms. *Molecular Metabolism*, 3(2), 94–108. doi:10.1016/j.molmet.2013.11.006

14. Bappayya, S., Palasubramaniam, D., Layland, J., Hofferberth, S., Wilson-O'Brien, A., Palmer, S., ... Wilson, A. (2013). Circulating Soluble Receptor for Advanced-Glycation End-Products is Elevated with Heparin Administration and Not by Cardiovascular Disease. *Heart, Lung and Circulation*, 22, S8. doi:10.1016/j.hlc.2013.05.016

15. Moriya, S., Yamazaki, M., Murakami, H., Maruyama, K., & Uchiyama, S. (2014). Two Soluble Isoforms of Receptors for Advanced Glycation End Products (RAGE) in Carotid Atherosclerosis: The Difference of Soluble and Endogenous Secretory RAGE. *Journal of Stroke and Cerebrovascular Diseases*, 23(10), 2540–2546. doi:10.1016/j.jstrokecerebrovasdis.2014.05.037

16. Horvat, Š., & Jakas, A. (2004). Peptide and amino acid glycation: new insights into the Maillard reaction. *Journal of Peptide Science*, 10(3), 119–137. doi:10.1002/psc.519

17. Maillard, L. C. (1912). Action of amino acids on sugars. Formation of melanoidins in a methodical way. *Comptes Rendus*, 154, 66–68.

18. O'Brien, J., Morrissey, P. a, & Ames, J. M. (1989). Nutritional and toxicological aspects of the Maillard browning reaction in foods. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 28(3), 211–248. doi:10.1080/10408398909527499

19. Somoza, V. (2005). Five years of research on health risks and benefits of Maillard reaction products: An update. *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research*, 49(7), 663–672. doi:10.1002/mnfr.200500034
20. Ames, J. M. (2007). Evidence against dietary advanced glycation endproducts being a risk to human health. *Molecular Nutrition & Food Research*, 51(9), 1085–1090. doi:10.1002/mnfr.200600304
21. Ulrich, P. (2001). Protein Glycation, Diabetes, and Aging. *Recent Progress in Hormone Research*, 56(1), 1–22. doi:10.1210/rp.56.1.1
22. Miyazawa, T., Nakagawa, K., Shimasaki, S., & Nagai, R. (2012). Lipid glycation and protein glycation in diabetes and atherosclerosis. *Amino Acids*, 42(4), 1163–1170. doi:10.1007/s00726-010-0772-3
23. THORNALLEY, P. J., LANGBORG, A., & MINHAS, H. S. (1999). Formation of glyoxal, methylglyoxal and 3-deoxyglucosone in the glycation of proteins by glucose. *Biochemical Journal*, 344(1), 109–116. doi:10.1042/bj3440109
24. Dickerson, T. J., & Janda, K. D. (2002). A previously undescribed chemical link between smoking and metabolic disease. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 99(23), 15084–15088. doi:10.1073/pnas.222561699
25. Zhang, Q., Ames, J. M., Smith, R. D., Baynes, J. W., Metz, O., & Metz, T. O. (2009). A Perspective on the Maillard Reaction and the Analysis of Protein Glycation by Mass Spectrometry: Probing the Pathogenesis of Chronic Disease. *J Proteome Res.*, 8(2), 754–769. doi:10.1021/pr800858h.A
26. Drel, V. R., Pacher, P., Ali, T. K., Shin, J., Julius, U., El-Remessy, A. B., & Obrosova, I. G. (2008). Aldose reductase inhibitor fidarestat counteracts diabetes-associated cataract formation, retinal oxidative-nitrosative stress, glial activation, and apoptosis. *International Journal of Molecular Medicine*, 21(6), 667–676. doi:10.2964/jsik.kuni0223
27. Anguizola, J., Matsuda, R., Barnaby, O. S., Hoy, K. S., Wa, C., DeBolt, E., ... Hage, D. S. (2013). Review: Glycation of human serum albumin. *Clinica Chimica Acta*, 425, 64–76. doi:10.1016/j.cca.2013.07.013
28. Uribarri, J., Woodruff, S., Goodman, S., Cai, W., Chen, X., Pyzik, R., ... Vlassara, H. (2010). Advanced Glycation End Products in Foods and a Practical Guide to Their Reduction in the Diet. *Journal of the American Dietetic Association*, 110(6), 911–916.e12. doi:10.1016/j.jada.2010.03.018
29. Cerami, C., Founds, H., Nicholl, I., Mitsuhashi, T., Giordano, D., Vanpatten, S., ... Cerami, A. (1997). Tobacco smoke is a source of toxic reactive glycation products. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 94(25), 13915–20. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/9391127>
30. Yamagishi, S., Matsui, T., & Nakamura, K. (2008). Possible involvement of tobacco-derived advanced glycation end products (AGEs) in an increased risk for developing cancers and cardiovascular disease in former smokers. *Medical Hypotheses*, 71(2), 259–261. doi:10.1016/j.mehy.2008.03.020
31. Rahbar, S. (1968). An abnormal hemoglobin in red cells of diabetics. *Clinica Chimica Acta*, 22(2), 296–298. doi:10.1016/0009-8981(68)90372-0
32. Raghav, A., Ahmad, J., Alam, K., & Khan, A. U. (2017). New insights into non-enzymatic glycation of human serum albumin biopolymer: A study to unveil its impaired structure and function. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2017.03.086
33. Song, F., & Schmidt, A. M. (2012). Glycation and Insulin Resistance: Novel Mechanisms and Unique Targets? *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology*, 32(8), 1760–1765. doi:10.1161/ATVBAHA.111.241877
34. Akhter, F., Khan, M. S., Alatar, A. A., Faisal, M., & Ahmad, S. (2016). Antigenic role of the adaptive immune response to d-ribose glycated LDL in diabetes, atherosclerosis and diabetes atherosclerotic patients. *Life Sciences*, 151, 139–146. doi:10.1016/j.lfs.2016.02.013
35. Qiu, Y.-Y., Tang, L.-Q., & Wei, W. (2017). Berberine exerts renoprotective effects by regulating the AGEs-RAGE signaling pathway in mesangial cells during diabetic nephropathy. *Molecular and Cellular Endocrinology*, 443, 89–105. doi:10.1016/j.mce.2017.01.009
36. Stitt, A. W. (n.d.). The role of advanced glycation in the pathogenesis of diabetic retinopathy Introduction to diabetic retinopathy. doi:10.1016/S0014-4800(03)00035-2
37. Patil, K. K., & Gacche, R. N. (2017). Inhibition of glycation and aldose reductase activity using dietary flavonoids: A lens organ culture studies. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 98, 730–738. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2017.01.129
38. Tatone, C., & Amicarelli, F. (2013). The aging ovary—the poor granulosa cells. *Fertility and Sterility*, 99(1), 12–17. doi:10.1016/j.fertnstert.2012.11.029
39. Molyneux, R. J., Lee, S. T., Gardner, D. R., Panter, K. E., & James, L. F. (2007). Phytochemicals: The good, the bad and the ugly? *Phytochemistry*, 68(22–24), 2973–2985. doi:10.1016/j.phytochem.2007.09.004
40. Harborne, J. B. (Jeffrey B., Baxter, H., & Moss, G. P. (1999). *Phytochemical dictionary: a handbook of bioactive compounds from plants*. Taylor &

Francis. Retrieved from

https://books.google.com.sa/books?id=VCITWqQS_6MC&vq=vast+array&source=gbs_navlinks_4

41. Mildner-Szkudlarz, S., Siger, A., Szwengiel, A., & Bajerska, J. (2015). Natural compounds from grape by-products enhance nutritive value and reduce formation of CML in model muffins. *Food Chemistry*, 172, 78–85. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2014.09.036

42. Mestry, S. N., Dhodi, J. B., Kumbhar, S. B., & Juvekar, A. R. (2016). Attenuation of diabetic nephropathy in streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats by *Punica granatum* Linn. leaves extract. *Journal of Traditional and Complementary Medicine*. doi:10.1016/j.jtcme.2016.06.008

43. Lekshmi, R. K., Rajesh, R., & Mini, S. (2015). Ethyl acetate fraction of *Cissus quadrangularis* stem ameliorates hyperglycaemia-mediated oxidative stress and suppresses inflammatory response in nicotinamide/streptozotocin induced type 2 diabetic rats. *Phytomedicine*, 22(10), 952–960. doi:10.1016/j.phymed.2015.06.014

44. Sampath, C., Rashid, M. R., Sang, S., & Ahmedna, M. (2017). Green tea epigallocatechin 3-gallate alleviates hyperglycemia and reduces advanced glycation end products via nrf2 pathway in mice with high fat diet-induced obesity. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 87, 73–81. doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2016.12.082

45. Al-Qattan, K. K., Mansour, M. H., Thomson, M., & Ali, M. (2016). Garlic decreases liver and kidney receptor for advanced glycation end products expression in experimental diabetes. *Pathophysiology*, 23(2), 135–145. doi:10.1016/j.pathophys.2016.02.003

46. Koo, Y.-C., Pyo, M. C., Nam, M.-H., Hong, C.-O., Yang, S.-Y., & Lee, K.-W. (2016). Chebulic acid prevents hepatic fibrosis induced by advanced glycation end-products in LX-2 cell by modulating Nrf2 translocation via ERK pathway. *Toxicology in Vitro*, 34, 8–15. doi:10.1016/j.tiv.2016.03.013

47. Lin, J.-A., Wu, C.-H., & Yen, G.-C. (2017). Breadfruit flavonoid derivatives attenuate advanced glycation end products (AGEs)-enhanced colon malignancy in HCT116 cancer cells. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 31, 248–254. doi:10.1016/j.jff.2017.01.050

48. Hsia, S.-M., Lee, W.-H., Yen, G.-C., & Wu, C.-H. (2016). Capsaicin, an active ingredient from chilli peppers, attenuates glycative stress and restores sRAGE levels in diabetic rats. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 21, 406–417. doi:10.1016/j.jff.2015.11.043

49. Kim, Y. S., Jung, D. H., Lee, I.-S., Pyun, B.-J., & Kim, J. S. (2016). *Osteomeles schwerinae* extracts inhibits the binding to receptors of advanced glycation end products and TGF- β 1 expression in mesangial cells under diabetic conditions.

Phytomedicine, 23(4), 388–397.

doi:10.1016/j.phymed.2016.02.005

50. Kaewseejan, N., & Siriamornpun, S. (2015). Bioactive components and properties of ethanolic extract and its fractions from *Gynura procumbens* leaves. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 74, 271–278. doi:10.1016/j.indcrop.2015.05.019

51. Gupta, P., Jain, V., Pareek, A., Kumari, P., Singh, R., Agarwal, P., & Sharma, V. (2016). Evaluation of effect of alcoholic extract of heartwood of *Pterocarpus marsupium* on in vitro antioxidant, anti-glycation, sorbitol accumulation and inhibition of aldose reductase activity. *Journal of Traditional and Complementary Medicine*. doi:10.1016/j.jtcme.2016.11.001

52. Ramkissoon, J. S., Mahomoodally, M. F., Subratty, A. H., & Ahmed, N. (2016). Inhibition of glucose- and fructose-mediated protein glycation by infusions and ethanolic extracts of ten culinary herbs and spices. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 6(6), 492–500. doi:10.1016/j.apjtb.2016.01.016

53. Kuo, C.-T., Liu, T.-H., Hsu, T.-H., Lin, F.-Y., & Chen, H.-Y. (2015). Antioxidant and antiglycation properties of different solvent extracts from Chinese olive (*Canarium album* L.) fruit. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine*, 8(12), 1013–1021. doi:10.1016/j.apjtm.2015.11.013

54. Wang, W., Liu, H., Wang, Z., Qi, J., Yuan, S., Zhang, W., ... Jia, A.-Q. (2016). Phytochemicals from *Camellia nitidissima* Chi inhibited the formation of advanced glycation end-products by scavenging methylglyoxal. *Food Chemistry*, 205, 204–211. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.03.019

55. Justino, A. B., Pereira, M. N., Vilela, D. D., Peixoto, L. G., Martins, M. M., Teixeira, R. R., ... Espindola, F. S. (2016). Peel of araticum fruit (*Annona crassiflora* Mart.) as a source of antioxidant compounds with α -amylase, α -glucosidase and glycation inhibitory activities. *Bioorganic Chemistry*, 69, 167–182. doi:10.1016/j.bioorg.2016.11.001

56. Hafsa, J., Hammi, K. M., Khedher, M. R. Ben, Smach, M. A., Charfeddine, B., Limem, K., & Majdoub, H. (2016). Inhibition of protein glycation, antioxidant and antiproliferative activities of *Carpobrotus edulis* extracts. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 84, 1496–1503. doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2016.11.046

57. Salami, M., Rahimmalek, M., & Ehtemam, M. H. (2016). Inhibitory effect of different fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*) samples and their phenolic compounds on formation of advanced glycation products and comparison of antimicrobial and antioxidant activities. *Food Chemistry*, 213, 196–205. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.06.070

58. Picot, M. C. N., Bender, O., Atalay, A., Zengin,

- G., Loffredo, L., Hadji-Minaglou, F., & Mahomoodally, M. F. (2017). Multiple pharmacological targets, cytotoxicity, and phytochemical profile of *Aphloia theiformis* (Vahl.) Benn. *Biomedicine & Pharmacotherapy*, 89, 342–350. doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2017.02.031
59. Meenatchi, P., Purushothaman, A., & Maneemegalai, S. (2017). Antioxidant, antiglycation and insulinotropic properties of *Coccinia grandis* (L.) in vitro: Possible role in prevention of diabetic complications. *Journal of Traditional and Complementary Medicine*, 7(1), 54–64. doi:10.1016/j.jtcme.2016.01.002
60. Oyedemi, S. O., Oyedemi, B. O., Coopoosamy, R. M., Prieto, J. M., Stapleton, P., & Gibbons, S. (2017). Antibacterial and norfloxacin potentiation activities of *Ocimum americanum* L. against methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *South African Journal of Botany*, 109, 308–314. doi:10.1016/j.sajb.2016.12.025
61. Park, K.-H., Kim, S.-J., Kim, J.-Y. J.-R., Min, K.-J., Kim, J.-Y. J.-R., & Cho, K.-H. (2017). Cold-water extract of Korean Red Ginseng exhibits potent inhibitory effects against cholesteryl ester transfer protein activity and fructose-mediated glycation along with lipid-lowering activity in hyperlipidemic zebrafish. *Journal of Ginseng Research*. doi:10.1016/j.jgr.2017.01.005
62. Kuda, T., Eda, M., Kataoka, M., Nemoto, M., Kawahara, M., Oshio, S., ... Kimura, B. (2016). Anti-glycation properties of the aqueous extract solutions of dried algae products and effect of lactic acid fermentation on the properties. *Food Chemistry*, 192, 1109–1115. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2015.07.073
63. Yu, P., Xu, X.-B., & Yu, S.-J. (2017). Inhibitory effect of sugarcane molasses extract on the formation of N ϵ -(carboxymethyl)lysine and N ϵ -(carboxyethyl)lysine. *Food Chemistry*, 221, 1145–1150. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.11.045
64. Awasthi, S., & Saraswathi, N. T. (2016). Sinigrin, a major glucosinolate from cruciferous vegetables restrains non-enzymatic glycation of albumin. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 83, 410–415. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2015.11.019
65. Siriamornpun, S., Weerapreeyakul, N., & Barusrux, S. (2015). Bioactive compounds and health implications are better for green jujube fruit than for ripe fruit. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 12, 246–255. doi:10.1016/j.jff.2014.11.016
66. Perera, P. R. D., Ekanayake, S., & Ranaweera, K. K. D. S. (2015). Comparison of Antiglycation and Antioxidant Potentials and Total Phenolic Contents of Decoctions from Antidiabetic Plants. *Procedia Chemistry*, 16, 519–524. doi:10.1016/j.proche.2015.12.087
67. Bains, Y., & Gugliucci, A. (2017). *Ilex paraguariensis* and its main component chlorogenic acid inhibit fructose formation of advanced glycation endproducts with amino acids at conditions compatible with those in the digestive system. *Fitoterapia*, 117, 6–10. doi:10.1016/j.fitote.2016.12.006
68. Tupe, R. S., Kulkarni, A., Adeshara, K., Shaikh, S., Shah, N., & Jadhav, A. (2015). *Syzygium jambolanum* and *Cephalandra indica* homeopathic preparations inhibit albumin glycation and protect erythrocytes: an in vitro study. *Homeopathy*, 104(3), 197–204. doi:10.1016/j.homp.2015.02.009
69. Awasthi, S., & Saraswathi, N. T. (2016). Vanillin restrains non-enzymatic glycation and aggregation of albumin by chemical chaperone like function. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 87, 1–6. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2016.02.041
70. Shen, Y., Xu, Z., & Sheng, Z. (2017). Ability of resveratrol to inhibit advanced glycation end product formation and carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzyme activity, and to conjugate methylglyoxal. *Food Chemistry*, 216, 153–160. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2016.08.034
71. Alam, M. M., Ahmad, I., & Naseem, I. (2015). Inhibitory effect of quercetin in the formation of advanced glycation end products of human serum albumin: An in vitro and molecular interaction study. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 79, 336–343. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2015.05.004
72. Ashraf, J. M., Shahab, U., Tabrez, S., Lee, E. J., Choi, I., & Ahmad, S. (2015). Quercetin as a finer substitute to aminoguanidine in the inhibition of glycation products. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 77, 188–192. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2015.03.021
73. Li, X., Zheng, T., Sang, S., & Lv, L. (2014). Quercetin Inhibits Advanced Glycation End Product Formation by Trapping Methylglyoxal and Glyoxal. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 62(50), 12152–12158. doi:10.1021/jf504132x
74. Yoon, S.-R., & Shim, S.-M. (2015). Inhibitory effect of polyphenols in *Houttuynia cordata* on advanced glycation end-products (AGEs) by trapping methylglyoxal. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, 61(1), 158–163. doi:10.1016/j.lwt.2014.11.014
75. Shi, L. (2016). Bioactivities, isolation and purification methods of polysaccharides from natural products: A review. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 92, 37–48. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2016.06.100
76. Xu, Y., Liu, G., Yu, Z., Song, X., Li, X., Yang, Y., ... Dai, J. (2016). Purification, characterization and antiglycation activity of a novel polysaccharide from black currant. *Food Chemistry*, 199, 694–701. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2015.12.078

77. Liping, S., Xuejiao, S., & Yongliang, Z. (2016). Preparation, characterization and antiglycation activities of the novel polysaccharides from *Boletus snicus*. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 92, 607–614. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2016.07.014
78. Chaouch, M. A., Hafsa, J., Rihouey, C., Le Cerf, D., & Majdoub, H. (2015). Depolymerization of polysaccharides from *Opuntia ficus indica*: Antioxidant and antiglycated activities. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 79, 779–786. doi:10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2015.06.003
79. Jiang, X., Kuang, F., Kong, F., & Yan, C. (2016). Prediction of the antiglycation activity of polysaccharides from *Benincasa hispida* using a response surface methodology. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 151, 358–363. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2016.05.079
80. Yu, Z., Liu, L., Xu, Y., Wang, L., Teng, X., Li, X., & Dai, J. (2015). Characterization and biological activities of a novel polysaccharide isolated from raspberry (*Rubus idaeus* L.) fruits. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 132, 180–186. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2015.06.068
81. Wang, Z.-B., Chen, B.-B., Luo, L., & Yan, J.-K. (2016). Fractionation, physicochemical characteristics and biological activities of polysaccharides from *Pueraria lobata* roots. *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers*, 67, 54–60. doi:10.1016/j.jtice.2016.07.029
82. Li, X.-L., Xiao, J.-J., Zha, X.-Q., Pan, L.-H., Asghar, M.-N., & Luo, J.-P. (2014). Structural identification and sulfated modification of an antiglycation *Dendrobium huoshanense* polysaccharide. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 106, 247–254. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2014.02.029
83. Lv, L., Cheng, Y., Zheng, T., Li, X., & Zhai, R. (2014). Purification, antioxidant activity and antiglycation of polysaccharides from *Polygonum multiflorum* Thunb. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 99, 765–773. doi:10.1016/j.carbpol.2013.09.007
84. Zhou, S., & Decker, E. A. (1999). Ability of carnosine and other skeletal muscle components to quench unsaturated aldehydic lipid oxidation products. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 47(1), 51–5. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/10563848>
85. Hobart, L. J., Seibel, I., Yeargans, G. S., & Seidler, N. W. (2004). Anti-crosslinking properties of carnosine: Significance of histidine. *Life Sciences*, 75(11), 1379–1389. doi:10.1016/j.lfs.2004.05.002
86. Szwergold, B. S. (2005). Carnosine and anserine act as effective transglycating agents in decomposition of aldose-derived Schiff bases. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 336(1), 36–41. doi:10.1016/j.bbrc.2005.08.033
87. Han, C.-H., Lin, Y.-S., Lin, S.-Y., & Hou, W.-C. (2014). Antioxidant and antiglycation activities of the synthesised dipeptide, Asn-Trp, derived from computer-aided simulation of yam dioscorin hydrolysis and its analogue, Gln-Trp. *Food Chemistry*, 147, 195–202. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2013.09.109
88. Hipkiss, A. R., Michaelis, J., & Syrris, P. (1995). Non-enzymatic glycosylation of the dipeptide l-carnosine, a potential anti-protein-cross-linking agent. *FEBS Letters*, 371(1), 81–85. doi:10.1016/0014-5793(95)00849-5
89. Pfister, F., Riedl, E., Wang, Q., vom Hagen, F., Deinzer, M., Harmsen, M. C., ... Hammes, H.-P. (2011). Oral carnosine supplementation prevents vascular damage in experimental diabetic retinopathy. *Cellular physiology and biochemistry: international journal of experimental cellular physiology, biochemistry, and pharmacology*, 28(1), 125–36. doi:10.1159/000331721
90. Nagai, K., Nijjima, A., Yamano, T., Otani, H., Okumra, N., Tsuruoka, N., ... Kiso, Y. (2003). Possible role of L-carnosine in the regulation of blood glucose through controlling autonomic nerves. *Experimental biology and medicine (Maywood, N.J.)*, 228(10), 1138–45. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/14610252>
91. Zhang, S.-S., Wu, Z., Zhang, Z., Xiong, Z.-Y., Chen, H., & Huang, Q.-B. (2017). Glucagon-like peptide-1 inhibits the receptor for advanced glycation endproducts to prevent podocyte apoptosis induced by advanced oxidative protein products. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*, 482(4), 1413–1419. doi:10.1016/j.bbrc.2016.12.050
92. Shi, F., Bai, B., Ma, S., Ji, S., & Liu, L. (2016). The inhibitory effects of γ -glutamylcysteine derivatives from fresh garlic on glycation radical formation. *Food Chemistry*, 194, 538–544. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2015.07.140
93. Alhamdani, M.-S. S., Al-Kassir, A.-H. A.-M., Abbas, F. K. H., Jaleel, N. A., & Al-Tae, M. F. (2007). Antiglycation and Antioxidant Effect of Carnosine against Glucose Degradation Products in Peritoneal Mesothelial Cells. *Nephron Clinical Practice*, 107(1), c26–c34. doi:10.1159/000106509